

Involving students' perspectives in multilingual mathematics learning spaces

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In a small on-going participatory research project, we collaborate with mathematics teachers. The project has reached a point where we, both the researchers and the teachers, have come to recognize the need to involve students in the design of their mathematics learning spaces because their knowledges and experiences may provide a crucial contribution. Therefore, we investigate in what way the students, teachers and researchers may collaborate to design mathematics learning spaces to facilitate multilingual students' mathematics learning. Involving the students in designing socially just mathematics learning spaces necessitates particular methodological decisions and identifies challenges in need of careful attention.

Focus and significance of the project

Elev: [...] jag menar vi pratar arabiska på lektionen. Vi säger så här för att vår lärare är arabisk så han låter oss skratta på arabiska mycket och vi skrattar och vi blandar arabiska och så.

Student: [...] I mean we speak Arabic during the lesson. We say this because our [mathematics] teacher is Arabic, so he lets us laugh in Arabic a lot and we laugh and mix Arabic [and Swedish] and so.

(Alhadi Alhasani & Zaki, 2021, p. 38)

The quote above comes from an interview that two pre-service teachers conducted as part of writing their degree project. The student's mother-tongue is Arabic. She attends middle school in Sweden, where the language of instruction is Swedish. In the quote, she describes how her teacher promotes laughing in a mathematics class. That she could use her full range of language resources made us feel joy and sparked the hope for social justice in language-diverse mathematics classrooms. In an on-going small participatory research project with three in-service mathematics teachers from the south of Sweden, we have jointly decided to investigate in what way these teachers' students can be involved in the discussions on and design of their multilingual mathematics learning spaces.

Despite persevering efforts in Sweden to promote all students' first languages as a resource in mathematics learning, many students with other language backgrounds than Swedish cannot (or may not) use the full range of their language resources in school

Please cite as: Källberg, P. S., & Ryan, U. (2021). Involving students' perspectives in multilingual mathematics learning spaces. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 176–179). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5392018>

(Lundberg, 2019). Among other things, this influences the interaction in language-diverse mathematics classrooms (Ryan, 2019) and the multilingual students' foregrounds (Svensson, et.al., 2014). Previous studies have demonstrated in what ways teachers can design learning activities that involve the multilingual students' languages and cultures as resources for mathematics learning (Celedón-Pattichis, et.al., 2018; Planas & Setati-Phakeng, 2014), rather than viewing these languages and cultures as deficits, which often is the case (Gutiérrez, 2008; Källberg, 2018). Students are responsible, knowing, feeling, thinking and acting subjects. Students know about language diversity and mathematics learning. When taken seriously, their knowledges and experiences can make a crucial contribution to the establishment of learning spaces (Stith & Roth, 2006). This motivates us, both the researchers and the teachers, to involve the students in the design of their learning spaces. To develop the project along these lines, we aim to investigate how the students' perspectives can be incorporated in the design of learning spaces *by student participation* to enhance socially just mathematics learning opportunities for multilingual students. We recognize that external factors – for example, demands for summative assessment – position the students and teachers in ways that may limit the design of socially just mathematics learning spaces (Cabral & Baldino, 2019).

The participants in this project are the two authors, three mathematics teachers and their students. The teachers teach grade 4 and 8 (10- and 15-year-old students). Concept development and problem solving were identified by the participating teachers as areas in their teaching they wanted to develop, which, therefore, frames the project. The following two over-arching research questions guide the project:

1. How can the students, teachers and researchers collaborate to design mathematics learning spaces to facilitate multilingual students' opportunities to work with mathematical concepts and problem solving?
2. How do the participating students and teachers experience working together to design mathematics learning spaces to facilitate the students' work with mathematical concepts and problem solving?

Theoretical background

In the context of multilingualism, problem solving in mathematics class presents multi-dimensional challenges to students and teachers. For example, usually students need to read a text that mediates the problem to be solved. In other words, students usually approach problem solving as a matter of dealing with text-rich tasks. Word problems pose lexical and discursive challenges because of the use of concepts that range from subject-specific to everyday concepts. In addition, word problems in mathematics represent a very particular genre which students need to be familiar with to understand the problem posed. To add to this complexity, many mathematical problems are situated in the so-called everyday experiences and events, which suggests a cultural dimension to problem solving (Barwell, 2009). Language and culture are issues of, for example, communication, identity and epistemology because language and culture are matters of knowing and of knowledge (Ryan, 2019). Hence, to solve mathematical problems, multilingual students need to (re)produce

ways of knowing mathematics and mathematical concepts, and mobilize lexical, discursive and cultural resources across all their languages and cultures to do so. The notion of language-as-a-resource holds various epistemological potentials for multilingual mathematics activities as suggested in Ryan, Källberg and Boistrup's (2021) epistemological framework for multilingual mathematics activities. For example, the 'lever' potential when actualised, can move students from informal mathematics talk in their first language to formal mathematics talk in the language of instruction. Hence, this potential functions as a *lever*. The 'one new whole' potential draws on the theoretical construct of translanguaging and, therefore, constitutes prerequisites to produce new ways of languaging and knowing mathematics (Ryan, et al., 2021). Our assumption is that various epistemological potentials make different kinds of learning spaces available which influence students' and teachers' agencies and identities when they engage in multilingual mathematics activities.

Methodology

With the aim to develop innovative ways of facilitating learning spaces for multilingual students' work with mathematical concepts and problem solving, the project builds on a close cooperation between the teachers, their students and the researchers. We draw on ethno-mathematical knowledge to envision our cooperative meetings as 'barters', a way of perceiving

elements that other participants do not produce. Sometimes these elements are either exchanged or given as a gift [...] Every person involved in the barter returns home with something new gained in the barter. Roughly speaking, when people are engaged in a barter, tasks that only can be done with a joint effort are accomplished and the interdependence of the agents is emphasized, benefiting everyone. (Parra-Sanchez, 2017, p. 94)

To stage such 'barters', the students, teachers and researchers conduct workshops on themes that connect to the jointly identified problem solving in their multilingual classrooms. The workshops are designed to enable the participants to brainstorm new ideas and solutions in relation to the chosen theme (Alminde & Warming, 2019). In addition to the student-teacher-researcher workshops, the researchers and the teachers meet in seminars once a month. During the seminars, the researchers and the teachers discuss and reflect on the implementation of the outcomes of the barters in the classrooms.

We recognize that asymmetric power relations – for example, pertaining to authority, responsibilities and interests among students, teachers, and researchers – are embedded in our project. This necessitates being explicit about such asymmetries, making power relations visible and addressing them carefully. We look forward to learning from and discuss with the MES community how to handle asymmetric power relations ethically and responsibly in participatory research projects that involve students.

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